

Dual Targeting of Monomeric Tau and α -Synuclein Aggregation: A New Multitarget Therapeutic Strategy for Neurodegeneration

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ABSTRACT: Development of efficient multitargeted therapeutic strategies is crucial in facing the multifaceted nature of neurodegenerative diseases. Parkinson's disease (PD) and Alzheimer's disease (AD), the two most common neurodegenerative disorders, share a common hallmark of accumulation of misfolded protein aggregates which are Lewy bodies (LBs) and neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs), respectively. Tau protein and α -synuclein (α -syn), the precursors of LBs and NFTs, have demonstrated synergistic aggregation and neurotoxicity in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models. Herein, we validate for the first time dual targeting of monomeric tau and α -syn aggregation as an efficient platform for development of multitarget therapeutics for neurological disorders. Cellular FRET-based high-throughput screening for tau-binding compounds, followed by additional screening of the hits for their ability to impede α -syn aggregation identified MG-2119 as a potential lead. The high binding affinity of MG-2119 to monomeric tau was verified using cellular FRET assay, isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC), surface plasmon resonance (SPR), and microscale thermophoresis (MSH). Moreover, MG-2119 inhibited α -syn aggregation as revealed by Thioflavin T (ThT) assay and dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements. Interestingly, MG-2119 was capable of rescuing combined tau and α -syn-induced cytotoxicity in SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells in a dose-dependent manner. Less pronounced cell-rescuing effects were observed for single-targeted tau and α -syn aggregation inhibitors showcasing the superiority of the multitargeted approach described in this study. Satisfactory pharmacokinetic profile and low toxicity of MG-2119 hold promise for future optimization to develop potential therapeutics for neurological disorders.

KEYWORDS: *Tau protein, α -synuclein, neurodegeneration, multitargeted therapeutics*

Alzheimer's disease (AD) and Parkinson's disease (PD) are the two most common neurodegenerative diseases and the main cause of dementia.¹⁻⁴ The World Alzheimer Report 2019 estimated the presence of over than 50 million people globally living with dementia and expected the number would rise to 152 million by 2050.⁵ Tau, an intrinsically disordered protein expressed in 6 isoforms in human central nervous system, exerts a key cellular role in stabilizing microtubules.⁶ Tau hyperphosphorylation associated with neurological disorders results in its detachment from microtubules and accumulation in cytosol.⁷ Consequent misfolding of monomeric tau into oligomers then to paired helical filaments (PHFs) and eventually into neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs) in human brain is a main pathological hallmark for cognitive impairment associated with tauopathies.⁸⁻¹⁰ Tau aggregation is directly associated with *in vitro* cytotoxicity in neuronal cells and *in vivo* neurodegeneration.¹¹ Thus, targeting tau aggregation has evolved as a promising therapeutic strategy for neurological disorders.¹²⁻¹⁶ Recent studies reveal that early-stage tau oligomers are the main neurotoxic species in human brain rather than PHFs and NFTs.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ However, the majority of tau-targeting small molecules interact with tau fibrils and late-stage tau oligomers resulting in their failure in clinical translation. For example, methylene blue which advanced to phase III clinical trials based on tau aggregation inhibition, failed as a potential therapeutic for neurodegenerative

diseases.²⁰ Small molecules that interact with monomeric tau and consequently inhibiting the formation of neurotoxic tau oligomers are quiet rare.^{13,14,21} Thus, there is an unmet need to identify novel scaffolds that inhibit the transformation of monomeric tau into toxic tau oligomers.

α -Synuclein (α -syn) is an intrinsically disordered protein that is highly expressed in human brain.²² Aggregation of α -syn into fibril-like inclusion in cytoplasmic Lewy bodies is a neuropathological feature of PD.²³ Multiple lines of evidences support the contribution of α -syn aggregation to various neurological disorders.²⁴ The associated toxicity with α -syn misfolding has been widely investigated in cellular and animal models.²⁵⁻²⁸ Small molecules targeting α -syn misfolding via impeding α -syn oligomerization or disaggregation of preformed α -syn fibrils have proven to be promising scaffolds as neuroprotective agents.²⁹⁻³¹ Additionally, multi-targeted potential therapeutics focused on targeting α -syn have been reported.³²

The mixed pathology observed clinically in dementia and PD patients as revealed by co-occurrence of both Lewy bodies and NFTs supports the association between tau and α -syn aggregation in human brain.^{33,34} The interaction between tau and α -syn in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models results in enhancement in the oligomerization of each other.³³ and Cell models of synucleinopathy reveal that tau enhances α -syn and toxicity in neuronal cells.³⁵ Additionally, in

vivo models of synucleinopathy demonstrated that tau and α -syn exhibited synergistic neurotoxicity.³⁶ Mice overexpressing mutated α -syn were protected from cognitive and motor deficits upon treatment with tau oligomer specific antibody.³⁶ Development of multitargeted therapeutics has evolved as a promising strategy in targeting multiple pathways implicated in the progression of neurodegenerative diseases.³⁷⁻⁴⁰ Herein, we report the first example of a small molecule (MG-2119) as a potential therapeutic for neurodegenerative diseases *via* dual targeting of monomeric tau and α -syn aggregation. This study serves as a proof-of-concept for establishment of this dual targeting route as an effective pathway for the development of therapeutics for neurological disorders.

Screening approach of focused chemical libraries is an established route for the identification of multitargeted small molecules.³⁷ However, this method remains mainly unexplored in the discovery of therapeutics for neurodegenerative diseases given the low success rate of virtual screening and cell-free assays in identifying effective bioactive agents in cellular platform. In this study, we report successful utilization of screening approach in the discovery of dual targeted small molecule against both tau and α -syn aggregation. Our approach starts with cell-based high-throughput screening (HTS) using previously reported fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) assay to filter a large chemical library (10,000 compounds) based on the ability to impede cellular tau oligomerization (Figure 1).²¹ Utilizing a cellular HTS as a first step in our approach ensures that the resulting focused library possess cellular efficacy as inhibitors of tau aggregation. Subsequent screening of a smaller subset of compounds based on the first screen (195 compounds) for their ability to inhibit α -syn aggregation identified a small molecule with dual mode of function targeting tau and α -syn aggregation (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A schematic illustration of the workflow adapted in this study to identify small molecules targeting both tau and α -syn aggregation.

The FRET-based HTS utilized in this study is optimized for detection of early-stage tau oligomerization in cell based on 2 cellular FRET sensors expressing full-length wild type tau and fused to green and red fluorescent proteins (GFP and

RFP).²¹ Tau oligomerization results in intermolecular interaction between the 2 FRET sensors expressing tau in SH-SY5Y cells and consequently a FRET signal. Small molecules that binds to monomeric tau expressed on the sensors impede this interaction resulting in attenuated FRET signal.²¹ We performed HTS using DIVERSet library from ChemBridge (~10,000 compounds) in a single-dose screen (10 μ M). A small subset of compounds (195 compounds) were able to decrease FRET signal by more than 5 standard deviations (5 SD) lower than total mean.

We subjected the 195 compounds to thioflavin T (ThT) assay in a single dose screen (10 μ M) to identify inhibitors of α -syn aggregation. ThT is a highly sensitive fluorescent dye that exhibits a strong increase in its fluorescence emission corresponding to the transformation of α -syn oligomers into mature fibrils.⁴¹ MG-2119 (Figure 2A) exhibited ~4-folds reduction in the fluorescence signal of ThT after incubation with α -syn oligomers for 12 h at 10 μ M (Figure S1). Additionally, a concentration-dependent effect of MG-2119 on ThT fluorescence signal in monitoring α -syn oligomerization was detected (Figure S1). We evaluated the effect of MG-2119 on α -syn oligomerization in real-time monitoring using ThT assay. As shown in Figure 2B, incubation of MG-2119 (10 μ M) with α -syn oligomers (100 μ M) resulted in overall attenuated fluorescence signal of ThT over the course of 38 h incubation. Such effect is attributed to the ability of increasing concentrations of MG-2119 to inhibit the formation of larger α -syn aggregates as demonstrated by dynamic light scattering (DLS). As shown in Figure 2C, the average particle size of α -syn oligomers decreased from 151 ± 6.2 nm to 24.2 ± 1.2 nm in the presence of 50 μ M of MG-2119 showcasing its ability to impede α -syn oligomerization. The binding affinity of MG-2119 to α -syn oligomers was studied using microscale thermophoresis (MSH). A dose-dependent change in thermophoresis indicates a dissociation constant (K_d) of 1.95 ± 0.4 μ M for the interaction between MG-2119 and Alexa Fluor 647-conjugated α -syn oligomers (Figure S2).

Figure 2. (A) Chemical structure of MG-2119. (B) Variation in the emission intensity (I/I_0) of ThT in the presence and absence of MG-2119 (10 μ M) in response to aggregation of α -syn oligomers (100 μ M), $\lambda_{ex} = 440$ nm, [ThT] = 5 mM. (C) Changes in the average particle size of α -syn oligomers (100

μM) based on DLS measurements as a function of MG-2119 concentration. Error bars represent standard deviation ($n = 3$).

In FRET-based HTS, MG-2119 ($10 \mu\text{M}$) decreased FRET signal by $\sim 90\%$ in comparison to the untreated control. Dose-response evaluation of MG-2119 using cellular wild type (WT) tau intermolecular FRET biosensors revealed that it attenuates FRET in SH-SY5Y cells with half maximal effective concentration (EC_{50}) of $0.91 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{M}$ (Figure 3A). We next evaluated cellular FRET-based dose-response of MG-2119 using FRET biosensors expressing P301L tau rather than WT tau. P301L tau is generally more oligomeric than WT tau because of hyperphosphorylation.⁴² MG-2119 featured less efficient FRET attenuation in P301L tau model (EC_{50} of $4.59 \pm 0.27 \mu\text{M}$, Figure 3B) in comparison to WT tau model. Small molecules that mainly interact with tau oligomers altering their conformation are known to possess comparable efficiency in both P301L tau and WT tau cellular FRET-based models.²¹ Thus, these results suggest that MG-2119 interacts with monomeric tau resulting in slower oligomerization rather than direct interaction with tau oligomers.

Figure 3. Dose-response curves of MG-2119 in cellular tau FRET assay using (A) WT tau and (B) P301L. Error bars represent standard deviation ($n = 3$).

In order to investigate potential binding affinity of MG-2119 with monomeric tau, evaluation of the binding using isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) was performed. An exothermic interaction was demonstrated for the interaction of MG-2110 with WT tau ($\Delta H = -11893 \text{ cal/mol}$). In addition, the estimated K_d value for the bimolecular interaction was found to be $5.34 \pm 0.6 \mu\text{M}$ (Figure S3). We further tested binding of MG-2119 to monomeric tau using MSH. As shown in Figure 4A, concentration-dependent change in thermophoresis reveals that MG-2119 binds monomeric tau (fluorophore-labeled) with an estimated K_d $3.57 \pm 0.14 \mu\text{M}$. Additionally, surface plasmon resonance (SPR) was utilized in studying the interaction of MG-2119 with monomeric tau. Flowing a solution of MG-2119 over a monomeric tau immobilized on chip demonstrated dose-dependent

binding with K_d $1.34 \pm 0.35 \mu\text{M}$ (Figure 4B). All these results come in good agreement with high binding affinity of MG-2119 to monomeric tau.

Figure 4. (A) Dose-response curve of MG-2119 binding to WT tau measured by MSH. (B) SPR binding curve for MG-2119 to WT tau. Error bars represent standard deviation ($n = 3$).

The binding mode of MG-2119 on monomeric tau was predicted using a 75 conformers ensemble (see Methods). The tau monomer is highly disordered, assuming a random coil structure,⁴³ in such a way that no well-defined binding site can be detected on its surface. For this reason, blind docking was performed exploring the full-length protein. The ten best docked poses (Figure S4) indicate that, owing to the simultaneous presence of aromatic rings and polar groups, MG-2119 binds through a combination of hydrophobic interactions, involving residues such as LEU, VAL, ILE and HIS (π -stacking), and hydrogen bonds involving both the side chains of polar residues such as ASN and LYS and the backbone. We observed that rather than targeting a specific sequence, MG-2119 binds into the transient pockets generated by the tau monomer folding over itself. These regions, which are denser compared to the extended coil, provide a larger number of stabilizing contacts. An interesting result is shown in Figure 5: in this particular conformation, the tau monomer presents a β -hairpin motif. MG-2119 binds laterally to this motif. We hypothesize that, owing to the steric hindrance provided by the aromatic rings, MG-2119 can interfere with monomer folding and recruiting into the growing fibril.

Figure 5. Predicted binding of MG-2119 on a β hairpin motif of the tau monomer.

Given that we have demonstrated the dual mode of action of MG-2119 by impeding both tau and α -syn oligomerization, we next evaluated the effect of MG-2119 on induced cytotoxicity in SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells. An established cell model of tauopathy in SH-SY5Y cells was used with a modification of co-incubation with α -syn oligomers to achieve induced toxicity by both tau and α -syn oligomerization.²¹ As shown in Fig. 6, MG-2119 reduces the induced toxicity in SH-SY5Y cells in a dose dependent manner. Interestingly, cellular screening of squalamine (inhibitor of α -syn aggregation)³¹ and MK-886 (inhibitor of tau aggregation)²¹ resulted in higher cytotoxicity in SH-SY5Y cells in comparison to MG-2119 (Figure 6). These results further validate dual targeting of tau and α -syn aggregation as a promising approach for developing of potential therapeutics of neurodegenerative diseases in comparison to single-targeted therapeutics against either pathway.

Figure 6. Cell viability % as determined by MTT assay in the presence of increasing concentrations of MG-2119, squalamine, and MK-886. Error bars represent standard deviation ($n = 3$, * $p < 0.05$ relative to untreated cells).

In order to verify the likelihood of success of MG-2119 as a potential therapeutic for neurodegenerative diseases, the ability of MG-2119 to cross the blood–brain barrier (BBB) was evaluated using the parallel artificial membrane permeability assay for BBB (PAMPA-BBB). Penetration ability of MG-2119 to BBB is expressed as effective permeability (Pe , cm/s) (Table S1). The assay was validated by using caffeine (a compound with low passive permeability) and

donepezil (a drug with high passive permeability). MG-2119 demonstrated Pe value of 29.4×10^{-6} cm/s which reveals high potential for crossing BBB. Therefore, this study further validates MG-2119 as a potential lead for further structural modifications to develop multitargeted therapeutics for neurodegenerative diseases. Additionally, preliminary pharmacokinetic properties of MG-2119 were evaluated (Table S2). MG-2119 featured high stability in simulated intestinal fluid pH 6.5 and moderate stability in gastric fluid pH 1.6. Moreover, ~99% of MG-2119 was intact upon incubation with human plasma for 2 hours showcasing high metabolic stability. CACO-2 cells permeability demonstrated high permeability of MG-2119 with no significant efflux. Importantly, MG-2119 (100 μ M) had no impact on the viability of HEL 299 normal human cell line. Collectively, the preliminary pharmacokinetic profiling of MG-2119 reported herein (Table S2) holds promise for its suitability for in vivo evaluation in animal models as a potential therapeutic of neurological disorders.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we have explored dual targeting of tau and α -syn aggregation by multitargeted small molecules as a novel approach in the development of therapeutics of neurodegenerative diseases. Cellular HTS for inhibitors of tau oligomerization followed by screening of the hits for the ability to impede α -syn aggregation identified MG-2119 as a potential lead. Cellular evaluation of MG-2119 revealed preferential rescuing of tau and α -syn-induced cytotoxicity in SH-SY5Y cells in comparison to squalamine (inhibitor of α -syn aggregation) and MK-886 (inhibitor of tau aggregation).

Methods

Cellular tau HTS

The assay was done using DIVERSet library from ChemBridge (~10,000 compounds) in a single-dose format (10 μ M) adopting the procedure previously described for the screen as well as transfection of cells with tau-GFP/RFP.²¹ Expression of tau-GFP/RFP in SH-SY5Y cells was confirmed using fluorescence microscopy. Compounds from the chemical library were dispensed as DMSO stock solutions (50 nL) to the 384-well plates (PN 781209, Greiner Bio-One) at a final concentration of 10 mM. Cells (1 millions cell/mL concentration) were dispensed to the assay plates (50 mL/well) and the plates were incubated for 2 hours at room temperature. Lifetime measurements were done using an LF502 Nanoscan FLT-TRF (IOM, Berlin, Germany). Hit compounds were identified by the ability to attenuate FRET signal five times the standard deviation relative to the mean. Fluorescent compounds were removed from further evaluation for potential interference as false positives. We next evaluated the dose-response profile of MG-2119 and determined the respective IC_{50} value. The dose-response curve was analyzed by nonlinear regression using GraphPad Prism 8.0.2 (GraphPad Software, Inc., La Jolla, CA, USA). Each data point from this assay represents the average of three independent measurements. Error bars represent standard deviation.

SPR screening

BIAcore S200 was used for SPR screening of the affinity of MG-2119 to WT tau. Immobilization of WT tau (20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) on CM5 sensor chip (Biacore, GE Healthcare) was done by amine coupling using 0.4 M 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide hydrochloride and 0.1 M *N*-hydroxysuccinimide.

Stock solution of MG-2119 was prepared in DMSO at 1 mM final concentration. Samples were then serially diluted while maintaining final DMSO concentration to 5% in all tested concentrations. Tested compounds in HEPES (pH 7.5) containing 5% DMSO and 0.05% Tween20 were allowed to flow through both ligand-captured flow cells and reference flow cells at the same rate (30 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$) and contact time (120 sec). Solvent correction was included to avoid the impact of DMSO on surface plasmon effect during binding analysis. Extra wash of the flow system using 50% DMSO in HEPES buffer was then performed following each run. Kinetic analysis was performed at 25 °C. Equilibrium dissociation rate constant (K_d) values was calculated using Biacore S200 Evaluation software.

ThT assay

A stock solution of α -syn (1 mM) in HEPES buffer (pH 7.5) was filtered using 22 μm membranes. The potential hits from HTS (195 compounds) were added as 50 μL to 96-well plates at a final concentration of 10 μM . α -Syn and ThT in HEPES (total volume of 100 μL) were added to the plated compounds at 70 μM and 40 μM concentrations, respectively. The plates were agitated at 100 rpm and 37 °C for 12 hours. Th-T fluorescence was measured at the specified time by Biorad microplate reader using 450 nm excitation filter and collecting emission with 480-510 filter.

Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS)

Particle size distribution analysis was measured by DLS experiments using a Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS instrument.

Preparation of α -syn oligomers

See the supporting information.

Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC)

Stock solutions of WT tau and MG-2119 were dialyzed against HEPES buffer (pH 7.5) containing 100 mM NaCl. A final DMSO concentration of 2% v/v was added to both stock solutions. ITC experiments were performed using GE MicroCal iTC 200 isothermal titration calorimeter. Titration experiments were conducted by injecting MG-2119 (0.5 mM) over a sample cell containing WT tau (50 μM). The resultant heats per injection were subtracted from the data for the MG-2119/WT tau interaction. The data was fitted using non-linear least squares regression to obtain the enthalpy change (ΔH) and equilibrium binding constants (K_B) of the bimolecular interaction. Data were processed using MicroCal Origin software.

Microscale Thermophoresis (MST)

MST study has been performed as previously described.¹⁴

Docking study

Prediction of the binding of MG-2119 on monomeric tau was performed using the GOLD software.⁴⁴ Tau was modeled as a 75 conformers ensemble taken from previously published study.⁴³ For each conformer of the 130 residues long tau model, binding cavity origins were set with a regular stride at the alpha carbons of residues 1, 26, 52, 78, 104 and 130. From each origin, the cavity radius was set to 25 Å. MG-2119 is a racemic mixture; due to the highly disordered nature of the tau ensemble, we do not expect significant difference in the binding properties of the two enantiomers, so that only the R form was considered for the *in silico* analysis. The GoldScore fitness function was employed to rank the different poses. Planar trigonal nitrogens in MG-2119 were allowed to flip between *cis* and *trans* conformations during docking. Similarly, hydroxyl groups were allowed 180 degrees flips. Torsion angle distributions extracted from the Cambridge Structural Database were used to restrict the exploration of the ligand's conformational space.

Cell viability assay

SH-SY5Y cells were grown in Roswell Park Memorial Institute medium (RPMI) supplemented with 2 mM L-glutamine, 100 UI/mL penicillin, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ streptomycin and 10% (v/v) fetal bovine serum (FBS). Cells were maintained in culture dishes at 37 °C in a saturated humidity atmosphere containing 95% air and 5% CO₂. SH-SY5Y cells were plated at a density of 5 x 10⁶ cells/plate in 100 mm plates (Corning) and transfected with WT tau for 24 hours as previously reported.²¹ Transfected cells were plated (5000 cells/well) in 96-well plates (Corning). Tested compounds at various concentrations were added to the assay plates as well as negative controls (DMSO). Addition of α -syn oligomers (5 μM) was followed by incubation of the assay plates for 72 hours. Cell viability was determined by measuring mitochondrial activity using the MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazole-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay. After the incubation time, the medium was removed and cells were incubated with 100 μl MTT (0.5 mg/ml) for 1 h. After that, the solution was removed, the formazan formed solubilized in 100 μl of 0.1N HCl in 90 % (v/v) 2-propanol and the absorbance was measured at 570 nm using a microplate reader (BioRad 680, USA).

Pharmacokinetic profiling

See the supporting information.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

The Supporting information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at DOI:

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Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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